
Socio Economic Status of Rural Population An Income Level Analysis of Ruvale Village in Patan Tahsil

Dr. Sambhaji Kallappa Naik

Asst. Prof in Geography

Kakasaheb Chavan College, Talmavale. Tal-Patan

Corresponding Author – Dr. Sambhaji Kallappa Naik

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.15067462

Introduction:

The current situation of the society in developing nations is rapidly moving from poor economy to develop economy with the development of social condition. But these changes are not equal to all places. Basically rural areas are very less developed as compared to urban areas in terms of social, cultural and economic aspects. Lifestyle of an individual's are widely depended on their economic status. Hence, social position of the person is dominated by his/her income. No society or region can be developed with the exception of any part remaining lag behind. Proper socio-economic development can control the healthy and balanced growth of a region. Now a day, increasing educational level and perception of education has been changing the socio-economic status among the rural population. Socio-economic characteristics are the important tools to the measures of human development. It is a measure of an individual's or family's or group of people's economic and social position based on education, income, health, and occupation . Socio-economic is the most important determinant of the livelihoods as it influences levels of knowledge, skill and income conditions which mean for their living. Peoples' way of living is differ from one income group to another as their consumption power is also differ among income groups of population. According to

Dutton and Levine (1989), socio-economic status is “a composite measure that typically incorporates economic status, measured by income; social status, measured by education; and work status, measured by occupation”. Rathod & Ningshen (2012), noted that Socio-economic status is an economic and sociological combined total measure of a person's work experience and of family's economic and social position relative to others, based on income, education, and occupation . Krieger et al. (1997) define socio- economic position as ‘an aggregate concept that includes both resource-based and prestige- based measures, as linked to both childhood and adult social class position’. Socio-economic status refers to the position of individuals, families, households, or other aggregates on one or more dimensions of stratification. These dimensions include income, education, prestige, wealth, or other aspects of standing that member of society deem salient. Socio- economic status is often considered a personal demographic variable; however, Socio- economic status can also reflect aspects of an individual's broader environment. As a result, it can be measured at the individual level or the area level.

Objectives:

The main objectives of the study are as follows:

1. To study the demographic conditions by level of income of sample population in the study area.
2. To analyse the level of education among different income groups of population.
3. To investigate the housing situation by level of income of the sample population in the study unit.
4. To examine the overall socio-economic status by level of income of peoples in the study area.

Data Base and Methodology:

The present study is based on primary survey by which a sample of 80 households have been taken randomly for the analysis of socio-economic status of different income groups of population from the Ruvale Village of Satara district, Maharashtra. The relevant data were collected from demographic, social and economic aspects. All the collected data were converted into relative number such as percentage to observe the overall situation and divided all the sample population in five income groups on the basis of monthly per capita income to examine the socioeconomic status of different income groups of population in the study area.

The Study Area:

Ruvale village is located at the south-west part in Patan Tahasil at the latitudinal and longitudinal figures of 17°24'47"N and 73°88'94"E respectively. This is one of the most remote village in the

satara district. It is located 95 km away from the district headquarter Satara. The village falls under the Patan tahasil according to 2011 census, Ruvale has 320 households and 1180 total population [7]. The road connectivity of the village is very bad but there is no market in the village, only few small shops are located in the village. The economy of the village is predominately agriculture based.

Discussion:

The total population of 80 sample households is 484, among them, males occupied by 52.9% and rest of 47.1% is by females. In the study area, sex ratio is very low, only 891 females per 1000 males observed. Table 1 depicts that among total 80 households, majority of them (42.50%) belongs to very low per capita income (below Rs. 500), which contributes 44.8% of total population, followed by 38.75% households belongs to per capita income of Rs. 501 – 1000 and share 39.1% of total sample population, 10% of total sample households belongs to Rs. 1001 – 1500 per capita income and compose of 8.47% of total population and only 5% households of total sample households come under the per capita income of Rs. 2000 and above, and constitute 4.34% of total population and 3.75% of total sample households lies under per capita income of Rs. 1500 – 2000, which is 3.31% of total population. The number of population is gradually decreasing with the increasing of per capita income of the population.

Table 1: Population Distribution by Level of Per Capita Income

Per Capita Income (Rs.)		Households		Total Population		Male		Female	
No.	%	No.	%	No.		%	No.	%	
<500	34	42.50	217	44.8	113	44.14	104	45.61	
501-1000	31	38.75	189	39.1	102	39.84	87	38.16	
1001-1500	8	10.00	41	8.47	24	9.38	17	7.46	
1501-2000	3	3.75	16	3.31	6	2.34	10	4.39	
>2000	4	5.00	21	4.34	11	4.3	10	4.39	
Total	80	100	484	100	256	100	228	100	

Source: Field survey, 2022

Education is one of the most important helpful components of the people for enhance lifestyle by increasing per capita income. Table 2 reveals that 59.56 % of the total population of less than Rs. 500 per capita income are literate, followed by 66.47% of Rs. 501-1000 per capita income, 82.05% of Rs. 1001-1500 per capita income,

85.71% of Rs. 1501 – 2000 per capita income and 100% literate peoples are found under Rs. 2000 and above per capita income. Because of low level of literacy, scope of the work participation in non agriculture sector would be reduced and people cannot exit from primary activities, in which returns are very low

Table 2: Literacy rate by Level of Per Capita Income

Per Capita Income (Rs.)	Literate	Illiterate
<500	59.56	40.44
501-1000	66.47	33.53
1001-1500	82.05	17.95
1501-2000	85.71	14.29
>2000	100.00	0.00

Source: Field survey, 2022

Lifestyle of an individual's is purely dependent on the level of education. Marlin *et al.*, (2008) noted that low literacy levels have negative impacts on individuals (such as children, youth, adults and seniors), health and well being, community participation, training, labour force, employment, productivity, and economic development [8]. Table 3 and figure 1 reflect that in below Rs. 500 income group, maximum literate persons are pre secondary educated (41.28%), followed by primary level (33.94), secondary level (19.27%), higher secondary level (4.59%), and graduate level (0.94%) of education. In Rs. 501-1000 per capita income the share of literate persons are as follows: 35.65% are primary educated, 34.78% are pre secondary, 20% are secondary educated,

5.22% are higher secondary educated, and 4.34% are graduates. Between in Rs. 1001-1500 income group, most of literate peoples are pre secondary educated (34.38%), followed by primary level (21.88%) and secondary level (21.88%), graduate level (15.63%) and higher secondary level (6.25%) of education. Between Rs. 1501-2000 income group literate peoples are distributed by primary (25%), pre secondary (25%) and higher secondary (25%), followed by secondary level (16.67%) and graduate level (8.33%) of education. And Rs. 2000 and above income groups' literate persons are constitute by secondary level education is 28.57%, higher secondary is 23.81%, pre secondary is 19.05%, post graduate is 14.29%, graduate level is 9.52% and primary level is 4.76%

Table 3: Levels of Education by Level of Per Capita Income

Level of Education							
Primary	Pre Secondary	Secondary	Higher Secondary	Graduate		Post Graduate	Others
<500	33.94	41.28	19.27	4.59	0.92	0.00	0.00
501-1000	35.65	34.78	20.00	5.22	4.35	0.00	0.00
1001-1500	21.88	34.38	21.88	6.25	15.63	0.00	0.00
1501-2000	25.00	25.00	16.67	25.00	8.33	0.00	0.00
>2000	4.76	19.05	28.57	23.81	9.52	14.29	0.00

Source: Field survey, 2022

Figure 1: Educational attainment by level of per capita income of population in the study area, 2012

The occupation of an individual refers to his trade, profession, type of work etc. The occupational structure of a society is the product of a number of intimately related factors [9]. Occupation is a major factor to determine the economic status of an individual, as different type of occupation reflects different incomes. In the study area all people are actively engaged in cultivation. In spite of it, many of them are also engaged in other occupations like, business, service, etc. (Table-4). Among below Rs. 500 income group of people are engaged day labourer (47.06%) in agricultural fields, brick kilns, rice mills, etc. Between Rs. 501-1000 income populations are engaged as day labourer (25.80%),

business (25.80%) and other activities (6.45%). Among Rs. 1001-1500 income population's major occupation is business (62.5%) viz. Peddler of rice and jute, shopkeeper, etc., followed by service (12.5%) and other occupation (25%). Between Rs. 1501-2000 income populations are engaged in business (33.33%) and service (33.33%). And Rs. 2000 and above income populations are actively engaged in service sector (100%). They are mainly associated with teaching profession or clerical service and army police. As they all are educated, can link with tertiary sector, which reflects them a better social and economic position in the study area.

Table 4: Occupational Composition by Level of Per Capita Income

Occupation	Per Capita Income (Rs.)				
	<500	501-1000	1001-1500	1501-2000	>2000
Cultivators	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Day Labourer	47.06	25.80	0.00	0.00	0.00
Business	0.00	25.80	62.50	33.33	0.00
Service	0.00	0.00	12.50	33.33	100.00
Other	11.74	6.45	25.00	0.00	0.00

Source: Field survey, 2022

In rural areas, different types of house are found viz. pucca house, kutcha house and mixed type house. Types of houses distribution is solely determined by the income of an individual's or family.

Among below Rs. 500 income groups of people, kutcha type (97.06%) of houses is mostly found in the study area, followed by mixed type house (3.03%) and no pucca house is found in that income group of

peoples (Table 5), because of low income. Among income groups of Rs. 501-1000, kutcha type of houses are mostly found (83.87%), followed by mixed type houses (12.9%) and pucca houses (3.23%). Among Rs. 1001-1500 income group of peoples, distribution of kutcha and mixed type houses are equal (50% each). Among Rs. 1501-2000 income group, 100% people have

kutcha house, as they pay out their surplus earnings on education for their children. 100% pucca house are found in the Rs. 2000 and above income group of people, as they are 100% literate which reflects them to more earning by engaged in different non-agricultural activities. Among all sample household, only this group of people's enjoy a little better lifestyle.

Table 5: Type of houses by Level of Per Capita Income

Types of House	Per Capita Income (Rs.)				
	<500	501-1000	1001-1500	1501-2000	>2000
Pucca House	0.00	3.23	0.00	0.00	100.00
Kutcha House	97.06	83.87	50.00	100.00	0.00
Mixed House	3.03	12.90	50.00	0.00	0.00

Source: Field survey, 2022

Lack of proper sanitation is the major concern in India basically in rural areas of the country. Proper sanitation is most important for a healthy life. But lack of finance and awareness of rural population, very small people are getting facilitated of latrine. In the study area, uses of latrine are very few (Table 6). Among below Rs. 500 per capita incomes population, very few have pit latrine (5.88%) and remaining 94.14% population are used open space for their sanitation. Between Rs. 501-1000

incomes population, availability of flush latrine (3.23%) is very low, pit latrine (25.80%) and nearly 71% population have no latrine facility. Between Rs. 1001-1500 incomes group of people have flush latrine (12.5%), pit latrine (50%) and 37.50% have no latrine facility in their houses. Between Rs. 1501-2000 incomes people have pit latrine (33.33%) and remaining 66.67% have no latrine facility. And Rs. 2000 and above incomes population, all have flush latrine (100%).

Type of Latrines used	Per Capita Income (Rs.)				
	<500	501-1000	1001-1500	1501-2000	>2000
Flush Latrine	0.00	3.23	12.50	0.00	100.00
Pit Latrine	5.88	25.80	50.00	33.33	0.00
No Latrine	94.12	70.97	37.50	66.67	0.00

Source: Field survey, 2022

Many villages in India still did not getting the facility of electricity. In the study area, some people are getting facility of electricity and some are still in dark. Maximum percentage of households (75%) is electrified among Rs. 2000 and above

incomes population, followed by 66.67% among Rs. 1501-2000 incomes population, 50% among Rs. 1001-1500 incomes population, 48.39% among Rs. 501-1000 incomes population and 23.53% among below Rs. 500 incomes population (Table 7).

Table 7: Availability of Electricity by Level of Per Capita Income

Electrified Houses	Per Capita Income (Rs.)				
	<500	501-1000	1001-1500	1501-2000	>2000
Electricity	23.53	48.39	50.00	66.67	75.00
No Electricity	76.47	51.61	50.00	33.33	25.00

Source: Field survey, 2022

As saving is surplus earning, the lower income (below Rs. 500) population cannot save their earning because management of three times meals and cloths is challengeable task within this income. A small portion (5.88%) of population try to save a little bit and a small portion (32.35) of

population run insurance for marriage of their girls. But comparatively higher incomes (Rs. 1501-2000 and 2000 and above) population saves their earning for future needs and runs insurance for secure of life (Table 8).

Table 8: Savings by Level of Per Capita Income

Saving Status	Per Capita Income (Rs.)				
	<500	501-1000	1001-1500	1501-2000	>2000
Savings	5.88	12.90	50.00	100.00	100.00
Insurance	32.35	61.29	50.00	100.00	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2022

Conclusion:

The above analysis plainly indicates that overall socio-economic status of population in the village is not good. 44.8% of total sample population's monthly income is below Rs. 500 and only 4.34%'s is above Rs. 2000. The lower income groups of people mainly engaged in agricultural fields other places as day labour. Most of them are still not getting many facilities like electricity, safe drinking water, proper sanitation etc., where comparatively higher income peoples are getting some of these facilities. Although comparatively higher income population enjoy a little better life but lower income population's socio-economic situation is very risky due to mainly low level of literacy and low income resulting create many social issues.

Suggestion:

Following are the few suggestions for the improvement of socio-economic condition of population of the village:

- To provide primary health care services and creates awareness about health among the villagers.
- To provide electricity services to the all people of village.
- Job oriented programmes should be implemented in the village level.

- To introduce various employment programmes for the youth population to reduce the migration of unemployment.
- To provide small loans to the villagers to run various small household industrial activities.
- To introduce subsidies programmes for various activities, especially, agriculture, social services .
- To introduce various schemes for poor peoples of the village.

References:

1. Mustaquim, M., and Islam, M. (2014), Demographic and Socio-Economic Characteristics of Inhabitants of Udaypur Village, Malda District, West Bengal, *Indian Streams Research Journal*, Vol. 4, Issue I, pp. 1-13.
2. Dutton, D.B., and Levis, S. (1989), Overview, Methodological Critique, and Reformulation, in J.P. Bunker, D.S. Gomby, and B.H. Kehrer (Eds.), *Pathways to Health. Melno Park, CA: The Henry J. Kaiser Family Foundation*, pp. 29-69.
3. Rathod, G.R., Ningshen, A., (2012), Measuring the Socio-Economic Status of Urban below Poverty Line

- Families in Imphal City, Manipur: A Livelihoods Study, *International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research*, Vol. 1(12), pp. 62-69.
4. Krieger, N., Williams, DR., Moss, HW. (1997), Measuring Social Class in US Public Health Research: Concepts, Methodologies, and Guidelines. *Annu. Rev. Public Health* 18: 341–78.
 5. Bollen, A.K., Glanville, L.J., and Stecklov G. (2001), Socio-Economic Status and Class in Studies of Fertility and Health in Developing Countries, *Annu. Rev. Sociol*, 27, pp. 153-185.
 6. Lynch, J., & Kaplan, G. (2000), Socio-Economic Position. in L. F. Berkman, and I. Kawachi (Eds.), *Social Epidemiology*, New York: Oxford University Press, pp. 13-35.
 7. Primary Census Abstract of Malda district (2011).
 8. Marlin, A., Zwicker, G., Zappia, S., and Bruce, D., (2008), Impacts of Low Literacy Levels in Rural New Brunswick, *Report submitted to The Rural Secretariat, Agriculture and Agri-Food, Canada, March, 2008*.
 9. Chandna, R.C., (2010), Geography of Population: Concepts, Determinants and Patterns, *Kalyani Publishers, New Delhi*, p. 313.